

Effect of point of purchase advertising on impulse buying: A study from Pakistan

Author Details: Zaeema Asrar Mohiudin

Abstract

Different economies have different characteristics, such as our economy is a consumption oriented economy. Karachi is the biggest city of Pakistan and one of the most populous cities in the world. There are people from different income groups. This city breaks the records for different occasional shopping in the country. Keeping this view in mind, this study has been carried to investigate the motivation for consumption. Data has been collected from 100 respondents in different shopping malls, Weekday Bazars and regular markets. The study has highlighted the impact of point of purchase advertising on consumers' spending decision. To the best of our knowledge, it is the first study to capture the impact of point of purchase advertisement on impulse buying in the context of Pakistan. Results of the study disclose that 65% of the respondents are impulse buyers including both male and females. These 65% are attracted by every offer which has been offered or announced.

Keywords: Advertising, Impulse buying, Point of Purchase

Introduction

Impulse buying has now become an importance aspect for market researchers to understand the consumer behavior. The phenomenon can be defined as "an unplanned decision to purchase a commodity or service taken just before buying it". This decision is derived by various factors of the customer such as feelings, sentiments, occasion or event, promotion of the product etc.

Beatty and Ferrell (1998) described that time is the variables which increase impulse buying.

Giraud (2001) specified that gender of the individual has significant impact on impulse buying. The reason is that females are thought to be more impulse than males. The author also added that good mood of the customer is also a motivator for impulse purchase.

Dittmar (2001) elaborated another factor which leads to impulse purchase decision of the customer, that is materialism. This moral characteristic of the individual is a notion of self-completion or satisfaction by acquiring the commodity.

Mai et al. (2003) explained that age is another influencing factor in impulse buying because young people are more impulse than people at mature ages. Along with this, culture/ custom is also a persuasive factor in leading impulse buying.

Crawford and Melewar (2003) provided that store layout, attentive staff and atmosphere of the place are foremost elements in impulse purchase.

Wong and Zhou (2003) enlarged the factors by adding store type as a crucial element. For instance, impulse purchase takes place in grocery shops. Product price also allows individual for unplanned purchase decision.

Mai et al. (2003) reveals the importance of money, it is a critical element which enables a consumer for a positive demand. Authors also added that product category effect impulsive choice for a product.

Sharma and Sivakumaran (2004) found that enjoyment during shopping has an integral part in purchaser's decision. As it has been considered as way of restoring energy that is why purchaser does not stick to the list and take impulse buying decision.

Luo (2004) has obtained another characteristic of the individual while shopping. It is the group characteristic i.e. people in a group eat more. On the contrary, people with self-discrepancy buy material products in order to bridge discrepancy.

Above mentioned all variables are of immense importance while understanding consumer behavior regarding a purchase. The point of purchase advertisement is also a portentous element in influencing an individual's impulse purchase decision. This strategy induces buyer to benefit from the promotion activity at the point when he/she came to purchase. To confine a comprehensive analysis of the tool of earning profit this study has been taken out through survey.

Study objective

This research has been conducted with the objective to observe the consumer behavior towards impulse buying when an advertisement has been displayed at the shopping places. As Karachi is the biggest city of Pakistan consequently it has the largest number of buyers as well belonging to different economic classes. The study aims to capture the above-mentioned research objective to open the door for a comprehensive and effective policy formulation for businesses and also for the consumers.

Results and discussion

Demographic Profile

	Impulse Buyer	Not Impulse Buyer	Total
Gender			
Male	25(71%)	10(29%)	35(100%)
Female	40(62%)	25(38%)	65(100%)
Age Group			
18-25	10(67%)	05(33)	15(100%)
26-35	25(76%)	08(34%)	33(100%)
36-45	20(67%)	10(33%)	30(100%)
46 and above	10(45%)	12(55%)	22(100%)
Occupation			
Business	15(63%)	09(37%)	24(100%)
Service	15(65%)	08(35%)	23(100%)
Student	17(63%)	10(37%)	27(100%)
Others (Housewife etc.)	18(69%)	08(31%)	26(100%)

Above mentioned table contains the demographics of the respondents. Data has been collected from 100 respondents in different shopping malls, Weekday Bazars and regular markets. 65% of the respondents are female, from which 62% are impulse buyers and 38% are not. 25% of the respondents are male from which 71% are impulse buyers and 21% are not. 26-35 years' age group are impulse buyers. 36-45 years' age group is second impulse purchaser age group in the data followed by the 18-25 years' age group. 69% respondents are housewives and dependents (individual of any age group who do not work). 65% respondents belong to service sector. Individual from business and students both are 63%. The table above revealed somewhat balanced picture.

Results

We have collected data from 100 respondents on a structured simple questionnaire. The questionnaire contains 7 questions in total with 5 question have three options while two are open questions which required comments.

65% of the respondents said that point of purchase advertisement effect their shopping positively, i.e. they spend more.

Responding to second question they said that their shopping hours increase when they see an advertisement at the place where they shop in order to shop longer. On the contrary, 35% of the respondent including 10% of male respondent said that this kind of advertisement do not affect their shopping plan as they are not impulse buyers. Amongst 65% of the repliers including male and females, it has been observed that they are attracted by the discount given on the prices of the products.

35% female and 25%, are the people who also shop more as they heard about the schemes like buy 1 get 1 free and hidden prizes in the products.

The same percentage of the people in the above question, revealed that they run out of budget when they see an advertisement favorable at the point of purchase. The percentage of the impulse buyers are 65% that is why they are the people who are in favor of point of purchase advertisement.

Conclusion

Businesses are motivated by profits and consumers are the source of profit for them. Therefore, it is important for business owners to observe consumer behavior. There are various factors which leads a buyer towards impulse purchase. One the important tactics is promotion/ advertising. Point of purchase advertising strategy has been examined in this paper. It has been found that different tools of the point of purchase advertising strategy like discount price, schemes like buy 1 get1 free, prize hidden in the product boxes etc. are attractive perks to increase sales. It has also been found that if a customer is impulse buyer then he/she will avail every opportunity, in other words, they sales of that product will surely increase.

References

- Beatty, S.E. and Ferrell, M.E. (1998), "Impulse Buying: Modeling its Precursors", *Journal of Retailing*, 74(2):169-191.
- Crawford, G. and Melewar, T.C. (2003), "The Importance of Impulse Purchasing Behavior in the International Airport Environment", *Journal of Consumer Behavior*, 3(1):85-98.
- Dittmar, H. (2001), "Impulse Buying in Ordinary and Compulsive Consumers", In E.U.Weber, J. Baron, and G. Loomes (Eds.), "*Conflicts and Tradeoffs in Decision Making*", Press Syndicate of the University of Cambridge, UK, 110-135.
- Gemcon Group, (2011). History, <http://www.gemcongroup.com/history.php>, retrieved, January 5, 2011.
- Luo, X.M. (2004), "Group Dynamics of Impulse Buying: An Extended Social Facilitation Perspective", *Advances in Consumer Research*, 31:431.
- Mai, N.T.T., Jung, K., Lantz, G., and Loeb, S.G. (2003), "An Exploratory Investigation into Impulse Buying Behavior in a Transitional Economy: A Study of Urban Consumers in Vietnam", *Journal of International Marketing*, 11(2):13-35.
- Sharma, P. and Sivakumaran, B. (2004), "Impulse Buying and Variety Seeking: Two Faces of the Same Coin? Or Maybe Not!" *Advances in Consumer Research*, 31:260-261.
- Tinne, W. S. (2011). Impulse Purchasing: A Literature Overview, *ASA University Review*, 4(2):65-73.
- Wahida S. T. (2011), "Factors Affecting Impulse Buying Behavior of Consumers at Superstores in Bangladesh", *ASA University Review*, Vol. 5 No. 1, January–June, 2011
- Zhou, L. and Wong, A. (2003), "Consumer Impulse Buying and In-Store Stimuli in Chinese Supermarkets", *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 16(2):37-53.

Appendix

Questionnaire

This questionnaire is for a research paper designed to assess consumer impulse buying behavior at shopping places. Your information will be kept confidential and the responses will be aggregated for analysis. Your participation is highly appreciated.

Name(Optional):

Age: 1. (18 - 25) 2. (26 - 35) 3. (36 - 45) 4. (45 - Above)

Gender: 1. Male 2. Female

Occupation: 1. Business 2. Service 3. Student 4. Others

Keeping point of purchase advertisement in view, answer the following questions

Questions	Yes	No	No Response
1: Point of purchase advertisement effects your shopping positively.			
2. Point of purchase advertisement increases your shopping hours.			
3. Discount prices are attractive for you impulse buying decision.			
4.Schemes like buy 1 get 1 free, prize in the product etc. induce your impulse buying decision.			
5. This kind of advertisement leads you to run out of budget.			
Comments			
How do you see point of purchase advertisement? customer's view			
How do you see point of purchase advertisement? Owner's view			